

COMPARISON OF NARCISSISM LEVELS OF STUDENTS IN SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to compare body image and narcissism levels of students of Istanbul Gelisim University, School of Physical Education and Sports. Population of the study was constituted by students studying at Istanbul Gelisim University whereas the sample was represented by 81 students studying at Istanbul Gelisim University School of Physical Education and Sports who voluntarily participated in our study. "Narcissistic Personality Inventory" was used as data collection tool. The Inventory was developed in 2005 by Daniel R. Ames, Paul Rose and Cameron P. Anderson. It was translated into Turkish in 2009 by Salim Atay and validity and reliability study was conducted. For analyzing the data acquired, SPSS 20 was used. Single sample "Kolmogorov-Smirnov" test was applied to learn whether or not the data had a normal distribution while "Anova-Homogeneity of variance" test was applied to determine its homogeneity and it was seen that the data was homogeneous and had normal distribution. For analyzing data, descriptive statistical analysis, one way analysis of variance and tukey test were applied. It was found as a result of the study that narcissism scores of students studying exercise and sports were higher than those of the students studying coach training and recreation.

Keywords: narcissism, coach training, recreation, exercise and sports

1. Introduction

Narcissism is defined, in simplest words, as feeling extreme admiration for one's self physical and intellectual abilities. It has been understood from studies on narcissistic

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personality that people with narcissistic personality characteristics admire their own physical and bodily features extremely. Sports enables an individual to make a more positive self-assessment, contributing to physical and bodily development of the individual. Self-assessment and self-perception of persons who gain a beautiful and esthetical physique thanks to sports are different from those of nonathletic people. Importance attached to appearance, attractiveness, being beautiful and handsome by many societies not only today but also in the past, has unavoidably led to a desire to become nice and attractive, for many people. Therefore, people have started to make great efforts to look more beautiful and have an esthetical physique. (Tazegül and Güven, 2015)

Narcissistic people admire themselves extremely both physically and spiritually, think themselves superior, continuously expect admiration, interest and approval, believe that they will immediately be shown particular interest wherever they go and they deserve a superior position. It is an inevitable fact to be disappointed and hurt so often among such great narcissistic expectations. Self-esteem of a narcissistic person is fed with external interest, admiration and approval. The said persons cannot stand criticism but always expect praise. For that reason, their appearances and behaviours all shape for acquiring those. Their friendships are solely for deriving benefits in this respect since they exploit others in order to praise themselves, get above themselves and masquerade themselves as superior to others. Narcissistic people are known to be egoist and egocentric in their relationships as they fail to show empathy towards feelings, thoughts and needs of others (Öztürk, 2002: 436).

Narcissistic individuals are selfish, since they think they are unequalled and special people. Feeling of selfishness in narcissistic people manifests itself excessively in their belief that they deserve more. They are success-oriented. They seek an opportunity to increase self-value whenever they feel a little fear for the lack of success. Narcissistic people make efforts to look good, to feel special, successful, important and positive. Sometimes they have intrapsychic thoughts such as blaming current situation but not themselves for fantasizing about power or for failure. And sometimes, they have thoughts such as exploiting the other party in their relationships for self-benefit. (Campbell and Foster, 2007: 7).

Narcissistic athletes attribute their failure in competitions to referee decisions, inaccuracy of rules, audience, wrong tactics given by the coach etc.. They do not believe they lose because of their own faults.

The purpose of this study is to make a comparison between body image and narcissism levels of students of Istanbul Gelişim University, School of Physical Education and Sports.

2. Method

2.1 Research Method

In this study, quantitative research method was used. Quantitative research method is described as follows; it is the research method which objectivizes and puts forth facts and events in an observable, measurable and numerically representable format. Main purpose in quantitative studies is to measure social behaviours of people objectively by means of observations and tests and set them forth quantitatively (Gurbetoğlu, 2008).

2.2 Population and Sample

Population of the study was constituted by students studying at Istanbul Gelişim University whereas the sample was represented by 81 students studying at Istanbul Gelişim University School of Physical Education and Sports, who voluntarily participated in our study.

3. Data Collection Tools

3.1 Narcissistic Personality Inventory

Narcissistic Personality Inventory was developed in 2005 by Daniel R. Ames, Paul Rose and Cameron P. Anderson. It was translated into Turkish in 2009 by Salim Atay and validity and reliability study was conducted. In the first study conducted following pilot scheme, Reliability coefficient was determined as 0,57. Due to the fact that reliability coefficient was found below expected values, checking correlation of each factor with the scale, four statements which were found to be perceived negatively and not to contribute to the scale were revised. In measurements made after this modification, Reliability Coefficient rised to 0,652. In this case, Pearson Correlation between narcissism scores of NPI-16 and NPI-15 scales was measured in order to determine whether or not 15-question questionnaire of NPI could be used if desired and the value was found to be 0,987 (Atay, 2009).

3.2 Analysis of Data

For analyzing data, SPSS 20 was used. In order to know if data had a normal distribution, single sample "Kolmogorov-Smirnov" test and in order to assess if data was homogeneous, "Anova-Homogeneity of variance" test was applied. In case where the data was homogeneous and had a normal distribution, descriptive statistical analysis, one way analysis of variance and Tukey test were applied.

4. Findings

Table 1: Descriptive statistics finding

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Coach Training	15	7,33	1,87718
Exercise and Sport Sciences	43	7,86	2,53153
Recreation	22	6,90	2,56179

As a result of descriptive statistical analysis, narcissism score of students studying exercise and sport sciences was determined as 7,86 and narcissism score of students studying coach training was determined as 7,33 whereas narcissism level of students studying recreation was determined as 6,90.

Table 2: One way analysis of variance

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p
Between Groups	53,772	10,754	1,523	,186
Within Groups	1080,467	7,062		

As a result of variance analysis, a difference of statistically insignificant level was found.

Table 3: Comparison of narcissism levels with respect to Departments (Tukey Test)

(I) department		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	p.
Coach Training	Exercise and Sport Sciences	-,527	,796	,509
	Recreation	,424	,889	,634
Exercise and Sport Sciences	Coach Training	,527	,796	,509
	Recreation	,951	,696	,174
Recreation	Coach Training	-,424	,889	,634
	Exercise and Sport Sciences	-,951	,696	,174

When narcissism scores were compared with respect to departments, a statistically insignificant difference was found among all departments.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

According to result of descriptive statistics, it was found that narcissism scores of students studying exercise and sport sciences were higher than scores of students studying coach training and recreation. Considering these results, it is possible to assert that students studying exercise and sport admire their physical and intellectual abilities

more. A statistically significant difference was not discovered as a result of comparison of narcissism scores of students within the scope of sample with respect to departments. In consequence of literature review, studies which are parallel to data of the study were discovered. Tazegül finds in his study in 2017 that steroids increase narcissistic personality level of athletes. Klein (1987) states that nobody can be more narcissistic than body builders. Klein also indicates that they always tend to show-off with their proportionally esthetical bodies. Tazegül finds the narcissism score of the athletes as 8,6374 in his study (2017a). He finds in his study (2013a) narcissism level of athletes in weight lifting branch as $(7,283 \pm 2,786)$ and narcissism level of athletes in boxing branch as $(7,216 \pm 2,584)$. Tazegül indicates narcissism level of greco-roman wrestlers as $(6,750 \pm 2,777)$ in 2011. Tazegül and Ferah discover in their study in 2016 that there is a positive relationship between narcissism score and sports age of sportswomen. Carroll, in his/her study in 1989, finds that narcissism levels of athletes in body building branch are higher than those of non-athletic people and athletes in other branches. Davis et al. also find in 2001 that narcissists are extremely compulsive about their physical appearances. Tazegül and Güven find narcissism score of athletes in body building branch as $(8,1429 \pm 4,09980)$ in their study of 2017. Carroll (1989) discovers in his/her study in 1989 that athletes practicing body building develop more narcissistic characteristics compared to athletes and students in different sport branches. Brown (1997) states that athletes practicing body building develop more narcissistic characteristics than non-athletes.

In conclusion, it was found that narcissism scores of students studying exercise and sports were higher than narcissism scores of students studying coach training and recreation.

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